

Comparative Diagnostic Efficacy of Biomarkers in Bronchial Asthma: A Tertiary Hospital Based Case Control Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: In case of Bronchial Asthma, there are ample of unresolved issues regarding current diagnostic biomarkers in practice. Based on evidence supporting Eosinophil Derived Neurotoxin (EDN), as a promising biomarker, this study has been designed to examine the evolving role of biomarkers in a tertiary hospital.

Objectives: To assess levels of Complete Blood Count (CBC), C-Reactive Protein (CRP), Interleukin 6 (IL-6), Eosinophil Derived Neurotoxin (EDN) in patients of Bronchial Asthma in cases and in controls and to study comparative diagnostic efficacy of EDN with respect to CBC, CRP, IL-6.

Study design: Cross sectional Analytical, Case Control Study conducted in Government Doon Medical College & Hospital, Dehradun, and Uttarakhand, India.

Duration of study: 12 months

- 42 cases and 42 controls have been taken.
- CBC, CRP was measured in CELL-DYN Ruby analyzer and BA 400 analyser machine respectively. IL-6, EDN was measured by ELISA method,
- The data was analysed using SPSS Software,
- A ROC curve analysis was conducted to compare the performances of serum EDN level compared with blood eosinophil count, IL6 and CRP as indicators of bronchial asthma in cases and controls and other parameters with each other.
- A two-tailed p-value less than 0.05 has been defined as statistical significance.

Results: EDN showed better performance when compared with eosinophil count, CRP, IL-6 with increased area under curve and highly significant p value of [0.795, 0.001], [0.797, 0.002], [0.744, 0.008] respectively. EDN did not show significant performance in controls when compared with eosinophil count, CRP, IL-6.

Conclusion: Measurement of serum level of EDN along with other biomarkers in use may add a benefit and increase diagnostic efficacy of Bronchial asthma.

Keywords: Bronchial asthma, Eosinophil Derived Neurotoxin, Interleukin-6, C - reactive protein, Eosinophil count.

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Introduction

Respiratory diseases have been mostly the commonest public health burden across the globe. [1] Among them asthma is the widely spread disease that potentially attack people of all age, sex and race. [2] Bronchial asthma is a chronic

inflammatory disease characterized by hyper reactive bronchi, airway obstruction which is reversible and mucus production in excess that arises from an inappropriate stimulation of the immune system, especially by environmental

aeroallergens. [1,3] Within the past few years, it has evolved as the most common non-communicable respiratory disease which affects children worldwide. [4] Severe asthma is characterized by the necessity for treatment with high-dose inhaled corticosteroids, along with a secondary controller (such as systemic corticosteroids), either to forestall its progression to an 'uncontrolled' state or to manage it in cases where it persists as 'uncontrolled' despite such intervention. [5] The rate of the disease burden has always been evaluated in developed countries; the greatest public health challenge is on developing countries due to poor disease management, disease monitoring and poor evaluation of the disease progress. [6]

Its prevalence has increased over the last few decades with various contributing factors such as cigarette smoking, [7] household economic status [8] occupational work condition of the patients, residence of the patients, presence of vermin at household and family history of asthma. [9]

The prevalence of asthma varies widely among countries or geographical regions and also within countries with different geographies and socioeconomic strata. [10,11] According to the Center of Disease Control and Prevention report, an estimated 235 million people which include 6 million children are suffering from bronchial asthma worldwide [12] and potentially involving a further 100 million by 2025. [13]

According to inflammation type, asthma is divided into T (type) 2-high and T2-low. [14] T2-high asthma is one of the most prevalent endotypes or phenotypes, characterized by the activation of type 2 helper (Th2) cells, type 2 innate lymphoid cells (ILC2s), mast cells, basophils, and eosinophils, along with heightened production of type 2 cytokines such as IL-4, IL-5, and IL-13. [15,16], T2-low asthma is distinguished by neutrophilic or paucigranulocytic inflammation and the activation of Th1 or Th17 cells, ILC1s, ILC3s, and the release of various cytokines such as CXCL8 and IL-17. [17] C-reactive protein (CRP), produced by the liver in response to inflammation, is elevated in various respiratory diseases, including asthma. Elevated CRP levels in the sputum, serum, and bronchoalveolar lavage fluid of asthma patients, especially during exacerbations, indicate underlying airway inflammation. [18] Higher CRP levels during asthma exacerbations compared to stable disease suggest CRP could be a useful biomarker for predicting exacerbations and monitoring disease activity. IL-6 is a cytokine involved in both acute and chronic inflammation, produced by various cells in response to infection, injury, or stimuli. It mobilizes immune cells to inflammation sites and regulates cytokine and acute-phase protein synthesis. [19] Dysregulated

IL-6 signaling is linked to autoimmune diseases, inflammation, cancer, and metabolic disorders. [20] In asthma, IL-6 promotes airway inflammation and remodelling by recruiting immune cells and stimulating the proliferation of airway smooth muscle cells and fibroblasts. Although not a typical Th2 cytokine, IL-6 can influence Th2 responses by altering the Th1/Th2 balance, contributing to allergic inflammation in asthma. Clinical studies show promising results for IL-6 receptor blockade in certain asthma patients. Inhibiting IL-6 signalling may improve airway inflammation and help manage severe or refractory asthma. [21]

Eosinophils, a type of white blood cell, play a crucial role in allergic asthma. [22] They are recruited to the airways upon allergen exposure, releasing pro-inflammatory mediators that cause airway hyper responsiveness, mucus production, and tissue damage. [23] Eosinophils also promote airway wall thickening and fibrosis by stimulating the proliferation of airway smooth muscle cells, fibroblasts, and epithelial cells. [24] They interact with T cells and dendritic cells to regulate immune responses in asthma. Targeting eosinophils has become a key asthma management strategy, with biologic agents like anti-IL-5 antibodies reducing asthma exacerbations and improving lung function in specific patients. [25]

Eosinophil Derived Neurotoxin (EDN), encoded by the RNASE2 gene, is the second most abundant protein in human eosinophils, with approximately 3.3 mg per million cells. [26,27], Found in various body fluids and tissues, EDN shares 67% amino acid similarity with ECP but has 100-fold greater ribonucleolytic activity, essential for its cytotoxic, neurotoxic, and antiviral properties. [28] EDN levels are consistently measurable in humans, indicating a potential role as a first line of defence against viral infections. [29,30],

In view of ample scope of further research in terms of unresolved issues regarding current biomarkers in practice including evidence supporting Eosinophil Derived Neurotoxin as a promising biomarker; the present study has been designed to study evolving role of biomarkers in a tertiary hospital.

Aim: Evaluate comparative diagnostic efficacy of select biomarkers in patients of Bronchial Asthma in a Tertiary hospital.

Objectives

Primary Objective: To assess levels of select biomarkers i.e Complete Blood Count (CBC), C-Reactive Protein (CRP), Interleukin 6 (IL-6), Eosinophil Derived Neurotoxin (EDN) in patients of Bronchial Asthma.

Secondary objective: To study comparative diagnostic efficacy of EDN with respect to CBC, CRP, IL-6 in patients of Bronchial Asthma.

Materials and Methods

Study design: Cross sectional Analytical, Case Control Study conducted in Government Doon Medical College & Hospital, Dehradun, and Uttarakhand, India.

Duration of study: 12 months (November 2022 – November 2023)

- 42 cases and 42 controls have been taken.
- CBC, CRP was measured in CELL-DYN Ruby analyser and BA 400 analyser machine respectively. IL-6, EDN was measured by ELISA method.
- The data was analyzed using SPSS Software (IBM Corp. Released 2013. IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 28.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.).
- A ROC curve analysis was conducted to compare the performances of serum EDN level compared with blood eosinophil count, IL6 and CRP as indicators of bronchial asthma in cases and controls and other parameters with each other.
- A two-tailed p-value less than 0.05 has been defined as statistical significance.

Inclusion Criteria: Adults aged 18-60 yrs who are having two or more of the following signs and symptoms consistent with Bronchial Asthma- Shortness of breath, chest tightness, wheezing,

trouble sleeping due to breathing issues, and coughing or wheezing attacks worsened by respiratory viruses.

Exclusion Criteria: Subject has a differential diagnosis of Bronchial Asthma, including large airway obstruction (e.g., foreign body, vocal cord dysfunction), small airway obstruction (e.g., viral bronchiolitis, cystic fibrosis), and other causes (e.g., recurrent non-asthmatic cough, aspiration, COPD). The subject is also a known carrier of a blood-transmitted disease or has a condition where phlebotomy is contraindicated.

Informed consent has been obtained using a patient information sheet in Hindi and English.

Results

The study aimed to identify the most reliable biomarker for diagnosing bronchial asthma through Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) analysis, assessing the sensitivity and specificity of each parameter.

The biomarker with the highest area under the ROC curve (AUC) was deemed the most reliable for diagnosing bronchial asthma. Results were as follows:

1. Eosinophil count when compared to serum EDN, IL-6 and CRP in cases, EDN showed better performance with area under curve 0.795 and significant p value of 0.001, followed by CRP and IL-6 with area under curve of 0.780, 0.557 respectively and p value of 0.002, 0.533 respectively.

Figure 1: Eosinophil Derived Neurotoxin showing increased area under curve followed by C - reactive protein and Interleukin-6

Table 1: Showing AUC and p value of EDN, CRP, IL-6 as (0.795, 0.001) (0.780, 0.002) (0.557, 0.533) respectively

Test Result Variable(s)	Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CRP	.780	.082	.002	.620	.941
IL_6	.557	.091	.533	.378	.735
EDN	.795	.080	.001	.638	.952

2. Serum CRP when compared to serum EDN, IL-6 and eosinophil count in cases, EDN showed better performance with area under curve 0.797 and significant p value of 0.002, followed by IL-6 and eosinophil count with area under curve of 0.788, 0.773 respectively and p value of 0.003, 0.004 respectively.

Figure 2: Eosinophil Derived Neurotoxin showing increased area under curve followed by Interleukin-6 and Eosinophil count

Table 2: Showing AUC and p value of EDN, IL-6, Eosinophil count as (0.797, 0.002) (0.788, 0.003) (0.773, 0.004) respectively

Test Result Variable(s)	Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
IL_6	.788	.071	.003	.648	.928
EDN	.797	.090	.002	.600	.953
Eosinophil	.773	.085	.004	.606	.939

3. Serum IL-6 when compared to serum EDN, CRP and eosinophil count in cases, EDN showed better performance with area under curve 0.744 and significant p value of 0.008, followed by CRP and eosinophil count with area under curve of 0.724, 0.601 respectively and p value of 0.015, 0.271 respectively.

Figure 3: Eosinophil Derived Neurotoxin showing increased area under curve followed by CRP and Eosinophil count

Table 3: Showing AUC and p value of EDN, CRP, Eosinophil count as (0.744, 0.008) (0.724, 0.015) (0.601, 0.271) respectively

Test Result Variable(s)	Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
EDN	.744	.079	.008	.589	.898
Eosinophil	.601	.088	.271	.429	.774
CRP	.724	.079	.015	.569	.878

4. Serum EDN level when compared to serum IL-6, CRP and eosinophil count in cases, eosinophil count showed better performance with area under curve of 0.754 and significant p value of 0.005, followed by CRP and IL-6, with area under curve 0.698, 0.690 respectively, and p value of 0.30, 0.37 respectively.

Figure 4: Eosinophil count showing increased area under curve followed by CRP and IL-6.

Table 4: Showing AUC and p value of Eosinophil count, CRP, IL-6 as (0.754, 0.005) (0.698, 0.030) (0.690, 0.037) respectively

Test Result Variable(s)	Area Under the Curve			Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
	Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
IL_6	.690	.086	.037	.521	.859
CRP	.698	.086	.030	.529	.867
Eosinophil	.754	.061	.005	.735	.974

5. Serum IL-6 when compared to serum CRP, EDN and eosinophil count in controls, CRP showed better performance with area under curve 0.682 but was not significant with p value of 0.133. Area under curve of EDN and eosinophil count are 0.641, 0.635 respectively and p values are not significant (0.244, 0.265 respectively).

Figure 5: CRP showing increased area under curve followed by EDN and Eosinophil count

Table 5: Showing AUC and p value of CRP, EDN, Eosinophil count as (0.682, 0.133) (0.641, 0.244) (0.635, 0.265) respectively

Test Result Variable(s)	Area Under the Curve			Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
	Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
EDN	.641	.109	.244	.427	.854
Eosinophil	.635	.143	.265	.354	.915
CRP	.682	.123	.133	.440	.923

6. Serum CRP when compared to serum IL-6, EDN and eosinophil count in controls, eosinophil count showed better performance with area under curve 0.774 and was significant with p value of 0.004. Area under curve of EDN and IL-6 are 0.523, 0.469 respectively and p values are not significant (0.810, 0.749 respectively).

Figure 6: Eosinophil count showing increased area under curve followed by EDN and IL-6.

Table 6: Showing AUC and p value of Eosinophil count, EDN, IL-6 as (0.774, 0.004) (0.523, 0.810) (0.469, 0.749) respectively

Test Result Variable(s)	Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
EDN	.523	.094	.810	.338	.708
Eosinophil	.774	.084	.004	.611	.938
IL_6	.469	.113	.749	.248	.690

7. Eosinophil count when compared to serum CRP, EDN and IL-6 in controls, CRP showed better performance with area under curve 0.678 but was not significant with p value of 0.092. Area under curve of IL-6 and EDN are 0.583, 0.484 respectively and p values are not significant (0.434, 0.883 respectively).

Figure 7: CRP showing increased area under curve followed by IL-6 and EDN.

Table 7: Showing AUC and p value of CRP, IL-6 EDN as (0.678, 0.092) (0.583, 0.434) (0.484, 0.883) respectively

Test Result Variable(s)	Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
EDN	.484	.102	.883	.285	.684
IL_6	.583	.115	.434	.358	.808
CRP	.678	.099	.092	.484	.872

8. Serum EDN when compared to serum CRP, IL-6 and eosinophil count in controls, IL-6 showed little better performance with area under curve 0.524, but was not significant with p value of 0.934. Area under curve of eosinophil count and CRP are 0.220, 0.122 respectively and p values are not significant (0.343, 0.201 respectively).

Figure 8: IL- 6 showing increased area under curve followed by Eosinophil count and CRP

Table 8: Showing AUC and p value of IL-6, Eosinophil count, CRP as (0.524, 0.934) (0.220, 0.343) (0.122, 0.201) respectively

Test Result Variable(s)	Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
IL_6	.524	.081	.934	.366	.683
CRP	.122	.058	.201	.008	.236
Eosinophil	.220	.085	.343	.052	.387

Discussion

The diagnosis of bronchial asthma is based on clinical symptoms, CBC, serum biomarkers, X-ray, CT scans, and response to anti-asthmatic drugs. In this study of 42 asthma patients and 42 controls from Doon Hospital, EDN demonstrated superior diagnostic efficacy with AUC and p-values of 0.795 and 0.001, respectively, compared to IL-6 (0.744, 0.008), CRP (0.797, 0.002), and eosinophil count (0.754, 0.005). These findings highlight

EDN's potential as a robust biomarker for diagnosing asthma and assessing its severity. EDN is a potent marker for eosinophilic inflammation in asthma due to its specific release by eosinophils, causing tissue damage and airway hyper responsiveness.

While EDN shows significant relevance in asthma, it performed poorly in controls, with an AUC of 0.641, 0.523, and 0.484 when compared to IL-6, CRP, and eosinophil count, respectively, all with

non-significant p-values. Conversely, IL-6 and CRP had slightly higher but non-significant performance in controls, indicating their non-specificity due to other factors like infections or allergies. These findings are consistent with previous literature suggesting the diagnostic utility of EDN in asthma. Studies by Choi et al. (2018) [31] and Park et al. (2019) [32] demonstrated elevated serum EDN levels in severe asthmatics and explored EDN-targeted therapy as a novel treatment approach, respectively. Our findings are also consistent with a study by Maciej Tota et al. (2023) [33] which elaborated the context of eosinophilic asthma, in which EDN levels correlate more strongly with disease severity and airway hyperresponsiveness compared to CRP and IL-6. Chakraborty et al. (2022) [34] found a positive correlation between EDN levels and blood eosinophil count, reflecting eosinophilic inflammation in asthma. Our study supports this, showing EDN's superior diagnostic performance (AUC 0.795, p 0.001) compared to eosinophil count (AUC 0.754, p 0.005). In "Severe eosinophilic asthma: a roadmap to consensus" (2017), Roland Buhl et al. [35] reported that high eosinophil counts strongly correlate with severe exacerbations and poor disease control, making them more reliable than EDN levels for assessing asthma severity. This contradicts our findings but includes treatment response, which our study did not address.

Our study found that serum CRP performed better than IL-6, EDN, and eosinophil count in distinguishing controls, indicating different diagnostic efficacies between cases and controls. The superior performance of EDN in asthma cases likely reflects its specific association with eosinophilic inflammation. These results highlight the need to evaluate multiple biomarkers in asthma diagnosis and management, considering patient-specific factors. While our findings support EDN as a valuable biomarker for asthma, further research is needed to validate these results in larger cohorts and assess its role in personalized treatment strategies.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study highlights Eosinophil Derived Neurotoxin (EDN) as a superior biomarker for diagnosing and assessing the severity of bronchial asthma compared to eosinophil count, CRP, and IL-6. EDN showed a higher area under the curve (AUC) and significant p-values, indicating its effectiveness in identifying and monitoring asthma due to its specific release by eosinophils and role in airway hyperresponsiveness and inflammation.

While traditional markers like CRP and IL-6 were less effective in our cohort, EDN's performance

underscores its potential for guiding treatment strategies, particularly anti-IL-5 therapies. Future research should validate these findings in larger populations and explore EDN's role in asthma pathogenesis and personalized treatment. Integrating EDN into clinical practice could enhance asthma diagnosis, monitoring, and management, improving patient outcomes and reducing healthcare costs.

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